

ENVIRONMENTAL-FRIENDLY FOOTBRIDGE MADE OF CFRP, GFRP AND TIMBER

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1 Introduction

Timber is one of the world's oldest construction materials. It was already used for timber bridges in Mesopotamia 3000 to 2000 B.C. [1]. The relatively high specific strength of timber (strength/density ratio) was often and still is an important criterion for its use. If treated correctly, timber has a long service life, as can be seen in timber bridges and multi-storey framework buildings in Asia or Europe that are over 400 years old [1]. In cases where the dimension or load bearing capacity of wood is not sufficient, combinations of fiber reinforced polymers (FRP) and timber are used today. Post-strengthening of timber structures with FRP has been very successful since 21 years [2]. The combination of these two materials will also allow new, innovative wide span constructions in future.

2 Concept and Construction

2.1 Concept

A bowstring arch bridge is an arch bridge, in which the outward-directed horizontal forces of the arch are borne as tension by the bottom chord, rather than by the ground or the bridge foundations [3]. Thrusts downward on such a bridge's deck as in this project are translated, as compression, by vertical struts from the deck to the polygonal bottom chord, tending to flatten it and thereby to push its tips outward into the abutments, like classical arch bridges. However in a bowstring- or tied-arch-bridge, these movements are restrained not by the abutments but by the bottom chord, which ties these tips together, taking the thrusts as tension, rather like the string of a bow that is being flattened. Therefore the design is called a bowstring-arch bridge. The elimination of horizontal forces at the abutments allows bowstring-

arch bridges to be constructed with less robust foundations. In addition, since they do not depend on horizontal compression forces for their integrity, tied arch bridges can be prefabricated off site, and subsequently lifted into place. The described bowstring-arch bridge reacts as system like a simply supported single-span beam bridge. However it is related to its dead load much stiffer.

2.2 Construction

The whole bridge (Fig. 1) was assembled in a laboratory hall of Empa. The originally flat glulam slab is stress-laminated. It is 12 m long, 3 m wide and 16 cm deep.

Fig. 1. Geometry and main dimensions of the bowstring arch bridge. All measurements are in [m].

The glulam slab is constructed by placing 16 cm wide (equal with depth of slab) and 4 cm thick sawn common spruce lumber laminations on edge. It was delivered in two 12 m long and 1.42 m wide glulam slab strips (Fig. 2). This two glulam slab strips were laid out in parallel to each other. 50 mm wide and 0.12 mm thick unidirectional thermoplastic CFRP

tapes with an E-modulus of 125 GPa were pulled on these two glulam slab strips (Figs. 3 and 4) in lateral direction. Then these two slab strips were pushed outwards with wedges in the central gap (Figs. 5 and 6). The spacing in longitudinal direction between the wedges was finally filled with spruce.

The stiffness (EA) of each of the 41 lateral tendons is 1.5 MN. The fibers used were Toray T700 and the matrix was a polyamide PA12. For the outermost lumber laminations on the longitudinal edges oak was used to avoid dents of the CFRP tapes into the lumber due to contact stresses. With this technique an efficient lateral pre-stressing was reached. It is causing the deck to act as a large orthotropic wooden plate.

Fig. 2. Two glulam strips each 12 m long and 1.42 m wide.

Fig. 3. As a closed loop welded unidirectional thermoplastic CFRP tape for lateral pre-stressing. Dimensions: 30 mm wide, 0.12 mm thick.

Fig. 4. The CFRP closed loops are ready to be pulled over the two glulam strips as lateral pre-stressing elements.

Fig. 5. Principle of the application of the lateral pre-stressing of the glulam slab with the help of wedges. The pre-stressing had to be conducted iteratively over the length of the slab and the wedges were glued at the final stage. The grey shaded parts are made of hard wood.

Fig. 6. Pre-stressing of the 41 closed CFRP loops.

Between the lateral CFRP tendons wooden spacers were fixed to the top of the glulam slab (Figs. 7-9). Later in the construction process the glulam slab was covered with a GFRP plate of 8 mm thickness. The tasks of this GFRP plate are to protect the glulam slab against rain and the thin, vulnerable CFRP tapes against damage, especially wear. The wooden spacers were arranged since nobody can ensure that the GFRP deck will be fully waterproof for the whole lifecycle of the bridge. In the case of a large leak it

Fig. 7. Lateral wooden spacers on top of the slab.

Fig. 8. Lateral wooden spacers on top of the slab.

Fig. 9. GFRP deck mounted on the wooden spacers.

could be seen when the water flows out at the longitudinal edges of the bridge. In the case of a small leak the water would evaporate in the air gap. Therefore it is the task of the spacers to avoid rottenness of the wooden bridge slab.

The bowstring-arch bridge concept was realized with six longitudinal arranged CFRP bowstrings and the above described glulam plate for the finally arch shaped bridge slab (Fig. 1). The bowstrings are composed of non-laminated pin loaded thermoplastic CFRP strap elements. The stiffness EA of each bowstring is 18 MN. It was the first time that such tendons were applied in a bridge construction.

Laboratory experiments and analytical modeling [4] have shown that there are severe stress concentrations in the region where the strap and the pin meet in the case of laminated pin loaded tendons (Fig. 10a).

Fig. 10. Conceptual design of pin-loaded strap elements.

The tensile resistance of the strap is therefore limited to about 50 % of the material's expected unidirectional strength. This is attributed to stress concentrations, which lead to premature failure. Furthermore, the production process for multi-layered laminated straps is not straightforward, if fiber misalignment is to be eliminated where the stress concentrations occur. An alternative option to reduce the undesirable stress concentrations, overcome the manufacturing difficulties and to reduce cost is the use of a non-laminated strap. The concept which has been pat-

ented [5] is shown in Fig. 10b. The CFRP strap now comprises a number of unidirectional reinforced layers, formed from a single, continuous, thermoplastic tape of about 0.12 mm thickness. The tape is wound around the two pins and only the end of the outermost layer is fusion bonded to the next outermost layer to form a closed loop.

The non-laminated strap element enables the individual layers to move relative to each other, which allows an equalization of forces in the layers as the strap is tensioned. The stress concentrations are reduced since the new structural form is more compliant than the laminated equivalent. Control of the initial tensioning process reduces interlaminar shear stresses so that a fairly uniform strain distribution in all layers can be achieved. The approach allows greater flexibility in terms of the geometry of the tendon, and it can be manufactured on site. Moreover, the concept is going to be less expensive because there is no consolidation process required.

An important aspect of non-laminated pin-loaded straps is the brittle nature of the carbon fibers. The stress, at which brittle fibers fail usually depends on the presence of flaws, which may occur randomly along the length of a fiber. A statistical approach of this situation involves conceptually dividing a length of fiber into a number of incremental lengths. The fiber fractures when it has at least one incremental element containing a flaw sufficient to cause failure under a given stress. This analysis is known as the Weakest Link Theory (WLT) [6]. The Weibull modulus, m , is an important parameter for characterizing the strength distribution of brittle solids. A low value of m (e. g. < 10) implies considerable uncertainty about the strength of a specimen. In practice, many ceramic materials exhibit Weibull moduli in the range from 2 to 15. Sommer et al. [7] reported values of $m = 5.25$ for strength properties of single carbon fiber filaments type Sigrafil C. Winistoerfer [4] measured for the best suited non-laminated strap elements Weibull moduli up to $m = 49$. This is a proof for a high system reliability of non-laminated CFRP strap elements. Ongoing outdoor creep tests are being carried out at Empa on specimens consisting of twenty-seven layers. Two specimens are loaded to 90 % of the average static load carrying capacity of equivalent straps. These specimens resisted more than six years these severe loading conditions.

After the prefabrication of the glulam slab and the CFRP straps, “the bow has been drawn”. For this longitudinal post-tensioning the flat bridge deck was supported at the two outer quarter-points (Fig. 11a) of its length and loaded with four concrete blocks at each beam end (Fig. 11b). This loading (approximately 32 kN per cantilever) resulted in the elastic deflection that was needed for the assembly of the struts and tendons. After putting these members into place the bowstring-arch was finally realized by the removal of the concrete blocks (Figs. 11c, 12, 13 and 14). The deflection is 1/75 of the span. The system is simple to install and operate, and time-consuming procedures such as bonding of post-tensioned elements and applying post-tensioning forces using hydraulic actuators are avoided. The total dead load of the bridge is 24.5 kN. The design load was set to 4 kN/m². All CFRP tendons were delivered by the Carbo-Link Ltd.

Fig. 11a. Flat glulam slab supported in quarter-points.

Fig. 11b. “Drawing of the bow”.

Fig. 11c. After the installation of the GFRP struts and the CFRP tendons the concrete blocks were removed.

Fig. 12. Bowstring composed of non-laminated thermoplastic CFRP strap elements, going through the hole in the glulam slab to the termination of the pin-loaded strap. The stiffness EA of each bowstring is 18 MN. The stiffness of the lateral tendons is 1.5 MN.

Fig. 13. Termination of a pin-loaded CFRP strap before tensioning. The length of a CFRP pin is 125 mm, and the diameter 40 mm (see also Fig. 12).

Fig. 14. Termination of a pin-loaded CFRP strap after tensioning. The fiber lay-up of the CFRP-pin is $0/\pm 45^\circ$ (Fiber Tenax UTS / EP).

The bridge deck is covered, as described in preceding sections, with a plate made of GFRP and the railing is also made of GFRP components. Most of the not load carrying joints of GFRP components are realized by gluing with an Epoxy type adhesive. After the assembly of the monitoring system components, the GFRP deck cover and parts of the railing, load tests were executed.

GFRP struts and CFRP tendons are shown in Figs. 15 and 16. The struts are designed a pendulum columns. The joint at the bottom ends of the struts and

the CFRP tendons is only based on contact and friction.

Fig. 15. There is no adhesive bond at the bottom ends of the struts and the CFRP tendons.

Fig. 16. The struts are designed a pendulum columns.

3 Installation

Fig. 17. Easy going installation of the bridge by crane.

The bowstring-arch bridge was set in place by a light crane that lifted the bridge over a water basin in front of the Empa head-office (Fig. 17).

6 Monitoring

6.1 Sensing Systems

Various advanced sensing systems have been installed to monitor the bridge. The system includes sensors for temperature, humidity, change of the width of the bridge, the tension of the CFRP bowstring tendons and a video system (Figs. 18, 19) for distributed deformation measurements [8].

Fig. 18. Video camera (inside circle) for photogrammetric measurements.

Fig. 19. Video targets fixed to the crossbeams connecting the struts at the quarter-spans, mid-span and the opposite abutment (reference) of the camera position.

6.2 Load Tests

Prior to installation of the bridge a load test was performed in the laboratory. Simultaneously the video surveillance system was tested. The load consisted of up to three concrete blocks each with a mass of about 860 kg (Fig. 20). They were placed perpendicularly to the longitudinal axis in the middle of the bridge. In Fig. 21 the measured deflections for the quarter-points and midspan are shown. For details see [8].

Fig. 20. Set-up for the load tests in the laboratory.

Fig. 21. Results of experimental load tests.

The bowstring-arch behaved during the load tests nearly perfect elastic. After unloading the deflec-

tions reached zero again. The comparison of the data of the quarter-points proves symmetrical deflections.

Fig. 22. Results of strain measurement and its exponential fitting curve for the glulam slab in lateral direction at mid-span. The bottom curve shows the seasonal deviation due to fluctuations of moisture and temperature.

Fig. 22 shows the results of strain measurements lateral to the glulam slab at mid-span. For details see [8 and 9]. These strains are typical for the whole slab and include all dimensional changes due to moisture, temperature fluctuations and due to creep of the glulam caused by the original lateral pre-stressing forces.

The moisture content of the “dry” wood approaches exponentially the average moisture. The time constant is approximately 180 days. The glulam slab has been slightly warping in lateral direction due the effects of moisture variation between opposing surfaces of the slab. As the top surface of the slab, covered by the GFRP deck, dries, the volume change causes the surface to shorten while the bottom of the slab above the water stays moist. Because the bottom surface stays moist, there is little or no shortening due to the effects of drying.

Due to the water take-up within the first two years there was a gain in swelling of $\epsilon = 0.38\%$. These strain measurements have been performed on the soffit of the glulam slab. Due to the described warp of the slab the average lateral strain will be a little bit less.

Taking into account that the stiffness EA of a lateral CFRP tendon is 1.5 [MN], there is an additional pre-stressing force of about 5.7 kN for each tendon. Since the pin-loaded CFRP straps face from an en-

gineering point of view no stress-relaxation [10], these additional forces are a real gain.

The bridge has been continuously monitored since its installation in March 2007 by a video photogrammetry system (Figs. 18 and 19) and is structurally performing perfectly.

Figs. 23 and 24 display the dynamic behavior of the structure due to an abrupt unloading.

The average person's walking pace on a foot bridge is about 1.7 Hz, or two steps per second. To avoid a feedback loop, the resonant frequency of a foot bridge should be higher than 4.5 Hz [11]. According to the results with the abrupt unloading experiments (Fig.24) is this condition with 4.6 Hz fulfilled.

Fig. 23. Oscillation duration due to abrupt unloading.

Fig. 24. Characteristic frequencies: first mode 4.6 Hz and second mode 6.0 Hz.

4 Costs

Fig. 25. Materials volume fractions a) versus cost b).

It is interesting to compare the volume fractions of materials and the corresponding cost for the whole bowstring-arch bridge (Fig. 25). The volume fraction (Fig. 25a) of glulam amounts to 93.8%, that of GFRP to 5.9% and that of CFRP to only 0.3%. On the cost percentage basis (Fig. 25b) glulam amounts to 18% (=12'000 USD), GFRP to 42% (=28'000 USD) and CFRP to 40% (=27'000 USD). The total price for bridges of this type in regular construction will be about 3'200 USD per square meter bridge surface.

5 Sustainability

By the increase of timber consumption the global CO₂ balance is favorable in two ways: (i) The use of timber in construction constitutes long term storage of CO₂; (ii) The use of timber in construction avoids the direct CO₂ emission due to production of steel or concrete. As shown in Fig. 25a, this bowstring-arch bridge made of materials by combination has a volume fraction of 94% of wood. This type of bridge is therefore from an environmental point of view very sustainable.

7 Conclusions

Laminated wood has developed into a high-tech material due to its homogenization. Nowadays, it can provide slender constructions and, when combined with advanced materials such as carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP), constructions with a very appealing architecture. Precisely in combination with new connecting elements, like pin loaded CFRP straps, it is possible to use laminated wood in highly stressed and dynamically loaded structures. Considering all the advantages of the described bowstring arch structure like lightweight, no corro-

sion, easy installation, good value and in the long run most important an excellent sustainability, there will be a very bright future for such structures.

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